

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY INFORMATION ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN VIETNAMESE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This study aims to assess the impact of social responsibility information on financial performance in Vietnamese enterprises. Data were collected by sending questionnaires to business managers or chief accountants of 300 enterprises in Vietnam and the number of votes that met the requirements for analysis was 256. Data were analyzed by applying the PLS-SEM model through SmartPLS 4.0.9.6 software. The research results showed that there was a significant positive impact of responsibility information on financial performance in Vietnamese enterprises. The research results can be a useful reference for managers of Vietnamese enterprises to have methods to use social responsibility information related to the aspects of employees, customers, local communities and business partners to provide information to improve the financial performance of enterprises.

Keywords: Information, Social Responsibility, Financial Performance, Impact.

1. INTRODUCTION

Promoting sustainable development is currently a common global goal, especially in the context of increasingly serious environmental damage. Many solutions have been implemented at both the international and national levels to limit and prevent negative environmental impacts on the economy, politics and society. A thorough assessment of environmental costs and benefits has become a necessary factor for businesses. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is increasingly closely linked to business operations. To aim for long-term and sustainable development, businesses need to develop appropriate business strategies, while strengthening social responsibility and environmental protection. In essence, social responsibility represents a comprehensive relationship between businesses and stakeholders. An effective CSR mechanism not only facilitates more active participation of stakeholders but also promotes the mobilization and coordination of resources, thereby creating shared value, making an important contribution to the realization of sustainable development goals (Zhang et al., 2020; Peng & Isa, 2020; Belas et al., 2022).

Many previous studies have come up with inconsistent conclusions on the relationship between CSR disclosure and corporate financial performance. Bellamy et al. (2023) studied 30 companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange and found that corporate performance was not significantly affected by CSR. Meanwhile, Alam and Tariq (2022) found a positive relationship between CSR and return on assets. In a study conducted in India by Sharama and Aggarwal (2022), a negative relationship between CSR and profitability was found. Thus, to date, there are inconsistent results on the relationship between CSR disclosure and corporate financial performance. From the above analysis, it can be seen that it is necessary to study the relationship between social responsibility information disclosure and financial performance in Vietnamese enterprises. In addition to the introduction, the rest of the paper is structured as

follows: Part 2 is an overview of the research; Part 3 presents the research methods; Part 4 presents the results of data analysis using the PLS Sem model; and Part 5 is the conclusion and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Responsibility

According to Bowen (1953), corporate social responsibility is understood as the obligation to pursue policies, make decisions and take actions that are consistent with society's expectations in terms of goals and values. Following this view, Beyer (1972) and Drucker (1974) argued that corporate social responsibility is the proactive implementation of community-oriented activities by businesses, because businesses generate profits from society while also consuming natural resources. Therefore, they need to be responsible for maintaining the environment, protecting resources and improving the quality of life for society. According to the definition of the United Nations Global Compact (UNGC, 2010), corporate social responsibility is a strategic policy initiative in which businesses commit to align their operations and development strategies with ten core principles in the areas of human rights, labor, environment and anti-corruption. From the above perspectives, it can be seen that corporate social responsibility is a comprehensive concept, including responsibility to shareholders, employees, the community, social justice and the environment. Implementing social responsibility not only contributes to enhancing the image and reputation of the enterprise but also brings economic benefits through reducing production costs, attracting customers and high-quality human resources. At the same time, social responsibility is also a tool to support enterprises to achieve business goals in a sustainable manner, contributing to solving social problems and fulfilling long-term commitments to the community. Thereby, enterprises can develop effectively and sustainably through the rational allocation and use of resources.

Financial performance

Murphy et al. (1996) stated that financial performance is the result of a business's operations reflected through the implementation of a number of financial indicators of the business. Measuring performance in terms of finance has always been the most popular measurement method in studies on corporate governance in general and accounting in particular (Hudson, 2001). Although a complete assessment of a company's financial performance must take into account many different types of measures, the most popular performance measure used in the field of finance and statistical inference is financial ratios (Farah Naz et Al, 2016). In finance, financial performance is measured to ensure the accountability of managers to shareholders. An important aspect of this involves measuring the profitability, market value and growth prospects of the company (Magara et al., 2015). Financial performance is often used as an indicator of the financial health of a business over a period of time. Financial performance is used to measure the overall health of a business and can also be used to compare between units in the same industry or sector. The financial performance of a company can be determined or measured in many different ways depending on the purpose of using information. Managers need to achieve profit goals towards sustainable development, they are interested in ROA,

ROE, ROS, revenue growth, profit. For owners and shareholders, their goal is to maximize investment, dividends, sustainable development; their concern is profit, market value, dividends, ROA, ROE, ROS, QTobin, revenue growth, profit... State agencies aim to collect enough and correct taxes; they are interested in revenue, profit, tax money of businesses,...

Related theories

According to stakeholder theory, the performance of a company depends on the effectiveness of management and the efficiency of resource use. According to Deegan and Gordon (1966), when evaluating stakeholders, it is necessary to emphasize making and evaluating agreed choices about the company's approach by using groups whose support is necessary for the sustainable development of the company. Guthrie and Parker (1990) argue that when analyzing and planning a business, the company needs to consider external influences that may conflict with the company's interests. At that time, managers need to anticipate a flexible strategic solution to meet the social needs of stakeholders. Stakeholder theory shows that in the stage of awareness of the environmental impact of production and business activities, managers need to pay attention to stakeholders. Accountants must consider the components of the environment and value the environment, and present this information in financial statements. Stakeholder theory suggests that the company operates not as a separate entity but also related to the interests of stakeholders. Enterprises are responsible for reporting environmental information to stakeholders, and at the same time building the image of the enterprise with stakeholders. Green accounting will fulfill this responsibility, and is a way to bring benefits to stakeholders while improving the efficiency of the enterprise itself.

According to the legitimacy theory, if a business wants to develop sustainably, it needs to meet social needs and contribute a lot to the community. The more businesses try and demonstrate their positive activities in social activities, the more they bring a goodwill image in the community. Besides the goal of maximizing profits, in recent decades, the responsibility to maintain nature and compensate for environmental damage is the responsibility chosen by businesses. According to Noodezh and Moghimi (2015), the legitimacy theory is widely used to clarify the goal of providing information about the environment and society. Under the pressure of society, businesses must operate within the framework of legal requirements before society and at the same time must provide social and environmental information to the community. When businesses are approved by the community, it is the motivation and opportunity for businesses to achieve operational efficiency.

3. RESEARCH MODEL

Corporate social responsibility has been shown to have many positive effects on businesses. According to Cochran and Wood (1984) and Waddock and Graves (1997), CSR helps businesses gain better access to valuable resources. In addition, it contributes to attracting and retaining high-quality human resources (Greening & Turban, 2000), improving the effectiveness of marketing products and services (Fombrun, 1996), creating unexpected opportunities (Fombrun et al., 2000), and helping businesses gain social legitimacy (Hawn et al., 2011). In addition, many studies have emphasized the role of CSR in moving towards

sustainable development. Social responsibility can help businesses reduce risks related to negative actions from the state such as legal regulations or financial sanctions (Hillman & Keim, 2001), attract socially conscious consumers, as well as access capital from investors interested in social responsibility (Kapstein, 2001). According to Freeman et al. (2021), sustainability in creating value for stakeholders depends on the ability to bring reasonable benefits to all factors of production - this is the foundation of sustainable development. In essence, CSR is a contractual link between businesses and stakeholders. Only by adapting to global development trends and accepting a role in implementing sustainable development can businesses achieve long-term competitive advantages (Chomvilailuk & Butcher, 2023). Carrasco-Monteagudo and Buendia-Martinez (2013) assert that integrating CSR into corporate culture is the key to improving financial performance and promoting innovation. In the same vein, Siltaloppi et al. (2021) argue that social responsibility should be viewed as a central, unique, and visionary strategy, linked to stakeholder management, environmental assessment, and addressing social issues. Lu et al. (2021) also emphasize that CSR can enhance competitiveness and ensure long-term stability for businesses. In short, CSR is a "win-win" mechanism that helps businesses both gain competitive advantages and aim for sustainable development goals. Social responsibility not only benefits shareholders but also creates value for other stakeholders such as employees, customers, suppliers, government and the community, thereby strengthening the position of enterprises in the modern economy. Therefore, the author proposes the following hypothesis: (H1) Information on social responsibility from the employee perspective positively affects the financial performance of enterprises; (H2) Information on social responsibility from the customer perspective positively affects the financial performance of enterprises; (H3) Information on social responsibility from the local community perspective positively affects the financial performance of enterprises; (H4) Information on social responsibility from the business partner perspective positively affects the financial performance of enterprises.

The scales of this study were inherited from Skudiene and Auruskeviciene (2012), Turker (2008), Latham and Pinder (2005), Williams and Anderson (1991).

Table 1: Coded scale table

Scale	Code	Sources
CSR on employee aspect Fair salary system Safe working environment Managers are straightforward and friendly with employees Employees have the conditions to develop themselves	CSRE CSRE1 CSRE2 CSRE3 CSRE4	Skudiene and Auruskeviciene (2012), Turker (2008), Latham and Pinder (2005),
CSR on customer aspect Procedures for handling customer complaints Provide honest information to customers Do not advertise or promote misleading customers	CSRC CSRC1 CSRC2 CSRC3	Skudiene and Auruskeviciene (2012), Turker (2008), Latham and Pinder (2005),
CSR on local community aspect Supporting local cultural and sports activities Charities Investing in community development	CSRL CSRL1 CSRL2 CSRL3	Skudiene and Auruskeviciene (2012), Turker (2008), Latham and Pinder (2005),
CSR on business partner aspect	CSRB	Skudiene and

Dealing Fairly with Business Partners Implementing Complaint Procedures for Business Partners Avoid Business Partners Behaving Illegally	CSRB1 CSRB2 CSRB3	Auruskeviciene (2012), Turker (2008), Latham and Pinder (2005),
Financial performance ROA ROE ROS	EF EF1 EF2 EF2	Hove et al. (2014)

Implementation process

The authors used a random sampling method to select 300 Vietnamese enterprises and sent out survey forms. Each enterprise was sent 01 survey form and the respondents were business managers or chief accountants.

The form of information collection was through Google form and sent to enterprises via email and social networking applications. The questions in the survey form applied a 5-level Likert scale: 1- Strongly disagree; 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neutral, 4 - Agree, 5- Strongly agree. After screening the response forms, the number of forms that met the requirements for analysis was 256.

With the aim of studying the impact of social responsibility information on corporate financial performance, the author uses quantitative research, specifically applying the PLS-SEM model through SmartPLS 4.0.9.6 software.

According to Henseler & Chin (2010), when applying PLS-SEM, the research model is evaluated through two steps: evaluating the measurement model and the structural model. First, the measurement model is evaluated through assessing the reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity of the measurement concepts in the model. Next, the structural model is evaluated through the coefficient of determination R2 and the path coefficient.

Description of research sample

Of the 256 surveyed enterprises, 112 were small and medium-sized enterprises with less than 100 employees, 98 were large enterprises with 100-200 employees, and 46 were enterprises with more than 200 employees.

In terms of ownership, 105 enterprises were private enterprises, 108 were joint stock enterprises, and 43 were state-owned enterprises. In terms of geographical areas surveyed, 121 enterprises were in the Northern region of Vietnam, 75 enterprises were in the Central region of Vietnam, and 60 enterprises were in the Southern region of Vietnam.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Measurement model analysis

Hair et al. (2014) suggested that the outer loading factor should be greater than or equal to 0.708, then the observed variable is assessed as quality. According to the survey results, 16 observed variables all have loading factors greater than 0.708, so all observed variables are assessed as quality.

Table 2: Composite Reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, Loading Factors and Average Variance Extracted

Constructs	Item	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Outer loadings	AVE
CSR on employee aspect	CSRE1	0.855	0.779	0.745	0.688
	CSRE2			0.760	
	CSRE3			0.736	
	CSRE4			0.790	
CSR on customer aspect	CSRC1	0.875	0.826	0.875	0.745
	CSRC2			0.743	
	CSRC3			0.786	
CSR on local community aspect	CSRL1	0.888	0.750	0.881	0.789
	CSRL2			0.807	
	CSRL3			0.763	
CSR on business partner aspect	CSRB1	0.847	0.729	0.873	0.659
	CSRB2			0.752	
	CSRB3			0.770	
Financial performance	EF1	0.881	0.729	0.890	0.787
	EF2			0.884	
	EF3			0.765	

After the observed variables were assessed to ensure quality, the author proceeded to assess the reliability of the scale. The reliability of the variables in the measurement model was assessed through two main indexes: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. Many researchers such as Hair et al. (2010), Bagozzi & Yi (1988) agreed that 0.7 is the appropriate assessment threshold. The values of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability in this study on CSR in terms of employees; CSR in terms of customers; CSR in terms of local communities; CSR in terms of business partners; Financial performance are all higher than 0.7. Therefore, the scales of the study ensure reliability.

To assess the convergence, the author relies on the average variance extracted (AVE). Hock & Ringle (2010) believe that a scale achieves convergent validity if the AVE is 0.5 or higher. Analysis of the measurement model shows that the AVE values of CSR employee aspects; CSR customer aspects; CSR local community aspects; CSR business partner aspects; Financial performance are all greater than 0.5. Therefore, the convergence of the variables is accepted.

Next, the author uses the Fornell-Larcker Criterion to test the discriminant validity of all measurement models. Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommend that discriminant validity is ensured when the square root of the AVE for each latent variable is higher than all the correlations between the latent variables with each other.

Table 3 shows that the square root of the AVE values of all variables CSR employee aspect; CSR customer aspect; CSR local community aspect; CSR business partner aspect; Financial performance are all higher than the correlation values between other constructs. Therefore, the discriminant validity between the variables in the study is ensured.

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	CSRE	CSRC	CSRL	CSRB	EF
CSRE	0.815				
CSRC	0.494	0.757			
CSRL	0.337	0.251	0.894		
CSRB	0.314	0.295	0.571	0.788	
EF	0.535	0.459	0.325	0.178	0.888

Structural model analysis

Before conducting structural model analysis, the author checked and evaluated the multicollinearity phenomenon between latent variables. According to Hair et al. (2019), if VIF is from 3 onwards, the model is highly likely to have multicollinearity. The analysis results show that the resulting VIF coefficients are all less than 3, so there is no multicollinearity in the model (Inner VIF values of CSRE are 1.000, Inner VIF values of CSRC are 1.125, Inner VIF values of CSRL are 1.256, Inner VIF values of CSRB are 1.534).

The results of structural model analysis show that the P-Values of the interactions (CSRE -> EF, CSRC -> EF, CSRL -> EF, CSRB -> EF) are all less than 0.05, so these interactions are statistically significant.

Table 4: Hypothesis Testing, R2 and f2

Hypothesis	Beta	SD	T-Value	P-Value	R Square Adjusted	f	Result
CSRE -> EF	0.545	0.055	9.366	0.000	0.382	0.400	Supported
CSRC -> EF	0.446	0.046	7.661	0.000		0.234	Supported
CSRL -> EF	0.207	0.071	2.898	0.004		0.031	Supported
CSRB -> EF	0.073	0.065	0.972	0.001		0.014	Supported

To assess the impact of one or more independent variables on a dependent variable in the SEM model, the author uses the adjusted R square index. The adjusted R square is 0.382, so the independent variables affecting it, including CSRE, CSRC, CSRL, CSRB, explained 38.2% of the variation (variance) of the EF variable. In addition, to assess the importance of the independent variable on the dependent variable, Cohen (1988) proposed the f square index. The f square index of CSRB on EF is 0.014, so this impact level is assessed as small. The CSRL variable has a medium impact on EF because it has an f square of 0.031. The importance of the CSRE variable on the EF variable is assessed as large because it has an f square of 0.400.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings of the study showed that all hypotheses were accepted, specifically, Social responsibility information from employee perspective positively affects the financial performance of the enterprise; Social responsibility information from customer perspective positively affects the financial performance of the enterprise; Social responsibility information from local community perspective positively affects the financial performance of the enterprise; Social responsibility information from business partner perspective positively affects the financial performance of the enterprise.

The research results provide an information base to help Vietnamese enterprises improve the use of social responsibility information and achieve business performance. Based on the research results, the author gives the following comments:

Firstly, in the context of sustainable development becoming an increasingly important factor in the development strategy of enterprises, the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility has become an urgent requirement for enterprises. One of the factors determining the success of CSR implementation is the understanding and commitment of business leaders and managers. Therefore, creating conditions for managers, leaders, and union officials to be trained and coached on CSR is very important. To effectively implement CSR, enterprises need to participate in training programs, seminars and projects related to CSR organized by universities, non-governmental organizations, and government agencies. These programs not only provide basic knowledge about CSR but also help managers better understand the benefits of CSR implementation, thereby promoting determination and implementation strategies in the organization. Organizations such as Industry Associations, VCCI, Business Office for Sustainable Development, as well as government agencies such as District and City People's Committees, are potential units to organize these training programs. In addition to participating in official training courses, businesses also need to proactively access information from various sources, especially mass media and the Internet. However, when accessing this information, businesses need to be able to analyze, select and apply accurate information that is suitable to their conditions and strategies. In addition to training and accessing information, visiting and learning from the experiences of typical businesses in implementing CSR is also an important method. This helps businesses learn from reality and better understand effective CSR strategies and models.

Second, in the context of increasing competition, implementing customer-oriented activities is an important factor that helps businesses not only maintain but also develop long-term relationships with consumers. For customers, businesses can immediately practice practical activities such as providing clear and accurate information about products and services, helping customers easily access the information needed to make purchasing decisions. In addition, businesses can increase access to products and services through programs to bring goods to rural areas or home delivery services, thereby increasing convenience and customer satisfaction. In addition, activities to improve the quality of goods and services are always a top priority. Businesses can implement this improvement step by step, to improve quality and better meet the increasingly diverse needs of consumers. At the same time, paying attention to customer satisfaction as well as enhancing customer care before, during and after sales will contribute significantly to building customer trust and loyalty to the brand.

Third, in the sustainable development strategy, enterprises not only focus on the interests of customers and the community but also need to pay special attention to the interests of employees. To implement Corporate Social Responsibility comprehensively, enterprises need to research and implement CSR activities in accordance with the aspirations and interests of employees. These activities not only ensure the legitimate rights of employees but also create a fair, healthy and developing working environment. One of the basic and necessary activities

in CSR for employees is not to use child labor and accept to hire people with disabilities, creating employment opportunities for all. In addition, enterprises need to apply disciplinary measures in accordance with regulations, not discriminate in terms of salary, benefits and other benefits of employees. Transparency in calculating and paying salaries, and assigning a person in charge of safety and health for employees, is an important factor in helping to build a fair and safe working environment.

Fourth, Corporate Social Responsibility is not only limited to employee or customer care activities but also extends to contributions to the community. For the community, in addition to contributing to social support funds, businesses can also participate in vocational training activities for workers. To improve the effectiveness of CSR activities, cooperation with specialized non-governmental organizations (NGOs) or non-profit organizations is an important solution. These organizations not only have experience and the ability to effectively implement community projects but also help businesses ensure that their contributions will truly bring practical benefits to the local community, helping to improve qualifications and create job opportunities for the community.

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